

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Progress in Neuropsychopharmacology & Biological Psychiatry

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/pnp

Exploratory study on plasma Acylglycerol and Acylethanolamide dysregulation in substance use and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder: Implications for novel biomarkers in dual diagnosis

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Acylglycerol
Acylethanolamide
Alcohol
Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder
Biomarker
Cocaine
Endocannabinoid
Machine learning

ABSTRACT

Substance use disorder (SUD) is a major global public health challenge, frequently co-occurring with psychiatric conditions such as attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). Endocannabinoid system (ECS) dysregulation has been implicated in both SUD and ADHD, but the interplay between these conditions remains poorly understood. This study investigates plasma concentrations of endocannabinoid-congeners in individuals with SUD, with and without comorbid ADHD, to identify potential biomarkers.

This exploratory study included 469 participants divided into three groups: (1) healthy controls ($n = 136$), (2) patients with SUD without ADHD ($n = 267$), and (3) patients with SUD and comorbid ADHD ($n = 66$). Plasma concentrations of 12 endocannabinoid-related molecules, including acylglycerols (2-AG, 2-LG, 2-OG) and acylethanolamides (AEA, DEA, DHEA, DGLEA, LEA, OEA, PEA, POEA, and SEA), were quantified using high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS). A multinomial Elastic Net regression model was applied to assess their biomarker potential.

Patients with SUD exhibited significantly lower plasma concentrations of 2-AG and 2-LG compared to controls, while most acylethanolamides were elevated, except for POEA and SEA. ADHD comorbidity was associated with lower concentrations of 2-AG, 2-LG, AEA, DGLEA, DHEA, and SEA, while PEA was elevated. Machine learning analysis identified AEA, OEA, PEA, and SEA as key biomarkers, achieving an accuracy of 72.1 % and an ROC-AUC of 0.77.

This study suggests distinct ECS alterations in SUD and comorbid ADHD, highlighting endocannabinoid-congeners as potential biomarkers. Future research should validate these findings in larger cohorts and explore ECS-targeted therapeutic interventions for dual-diagnosis populations.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpbp.2025.111350>

Received 9 October 2024; Received in revised form 28 March 2025; Accepted 30 March 2025

Available online 4 April 2025

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1. Introduction

The use of psychoactive substances represents one of the most significant global public health problems (Lo et al., 2020). Alcohol and cocaine are among the most prevalently consumed substances (OMS, 2019; WDR, 2021), with a substantial proportion of users eventually developing a substance use disorder (SUD) (Fuster et al., 2024; Koob, 2003). The development and progression of SUD are influenced by multiple factors, including biological sex and comorbid medical and/or psychiatric conditions (Becker, 2016; Fuster et al., 2024; Schuckit, 2006). Among the primary psychiatric comorbidities associated with SUD are mood disorders, anxiety disorders, psychotic disorders, personality disorders, and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) (Schuckit, 2006).

ADHD is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by a persistent pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity (Faraone et al., 2015; Schuckit, 2006; Waddell and McCarthy, 2012). It is particularly prevalent in childhood and adolescence, with a higher incidence among boys (Waddell and McCarthy, 2012), and persists into adulthood in approximately 60 % of cases (APA, 2014, s. f.; Aragonès et al., 2010). Moreover, ADHD has emerged as a significant risk factor for the development of SUD (Aragonès et al., 2010; Vaziri-Harami et al., 2024), as individuals with ADHD often exhibit distinct biological and cognitive characteristics that may contribute to this comorbidity (Lee et al., 2011; Vaziri-Harami et al., 2024). It is estimated that 20 % to 30 % of adults with ADHD have comorbid SUD. This co-occurrence complicates the clinical course, prognosis, and treatment outcomes. Among the substances most commonly associated with ADHD are alcohol and cocaine (Lee et al., 2011; Maxwell, 2013; Pérez de Los et al., 2011). The symptomatology of ADHD, particularly impulsivity and deficits in impulse control, predisposes individuals to experimentation and repeated substance use (Brandt et al., 2021). Both alcohol and cocaine may be used as a form of self-medication by individuals with ADHD (Carli et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2021). Specifically, alcohol is frequently consumed to mitigate symptoms of anxiety or inattention (Wang et al., 2021), whereas cocaine may be used for its stimulant effects, which can counteract the lethargy and difficulty sustaining attention often associated with ADHD (Carli et al., 2023). The interaction between ADHD and SUD creates a feedback loop that exacerbates the symptoms of both disorders. Furthermore, untreated ADHD has been linked to increased SUD severity, including higher relapse rates and lower treatment adherence (Kawata et al., 2023; Seitz et al., 2013).

In recent years, new therapeutic targets have been investigated to facilitate the early diagnosis and treatment of patients with SUD and its most prevalent comorbidities, including ADHD. The endocannabinoid system (ECS), a lipid signaling network comprising cannabinoid receptors, endogenous ligands (endocannabinoids), and associated enzymes, has emerged as a critical area of research. To date, two primary receptor types have been characterized and cloned: CB₁ and CB₂, both of which belong to the superfamily of G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) (Devane et al., 1992; Herkenham et al., 1990). The best-characterized endocannabinoids are anandamide (arachidonylethanolamide, AEA) and 2-arachidonoylglycerol (2-AG) (Devane et al., 1992; Sugiura et al., 1995), both of which are derivatives of arachidonic acid. Structurally, AEA belongs to the acylethanolamide family, which includes other bioactive fatty acid-derived mediators such as docosetraenoylethanolamide (DEA), dihomo- γ -linolenylethanolamide (DGLA), docosahexaenoylethanolamide (DHEA), linoleylethanolamide (LEA), oleylethanolamide (OEA), palmitoylethanolamide (PEA), palmitoleylethanolamide (POEA), and stearoylethanolamide (SEA). Conversely, 2-AG is classified as an acylglycerol, a distinct group of signaling molecules that are present in the central nervous system (CNS) at higher concentrations than acylethanolamides. Acylglycerols primarily exert neuromodulatory effects, particularly through cannabinoid receptor pathways. Other notable molecules within this group include 2-linoleoylglycerol (2-LG) and 2-oleoylglycerol (2-OG).

The ECS plays a crucial role in the modulation of various physiological processes, including neuronal development, immune function, metabolism, and emotional regulation (Bala et al., 2024). It has also been implicated in the pathophysiology of substance addiction, particularly due to the high expression of the CB₁ receptor in brain regions associated with motivation and addiction (Fuentes et al., 2024; Karimi-Haghighi et al., 2023). A growing body of evidence suggests that endocannabinoid signaling influences behaviors linked to alcohol and cocaine consumption. Preclinical studies have demonstrated alterations in cannabinoid receptors and ECS enzymes regulating acylethanolamides and acylglycerols within addiction-related brain regions, alongside changes in their circulating concentrations (Basavarajappa et al., 2003; Blanco et al., 2012, 2014; Serra et al., 2023; Serrano and Parsons, 2011). In humans, selective alterations in CB₁ receptors and fatty acid amide hydrolase (FAAH), one of the key enzymes involved in endocannabinoid degradation, have been observed in the ventral striatum of patients with alcohol use disorder (AUD) and individuals who died by suicide, highlighting the intricate relationship between the ECS and substance use (Vinod et al., 2010). Additionally, other studies have reported altered circulating plasma concentrations of acylethanolamides and acylglycerols in patients with SUD and high psychiatric comorbidity compared to healthy controls (García Marchena et al., 2016; García-Marchena et al., 2017; Pedraz et al., 2015).

In addition to its role in addiction-related behaviors (Serrano and Parsons, 2011), numerous studies have highlighted its involvement of the ECS in ADHD (Navarrete et al., 2020). The ECS participates in neural development and the modulation of impulsivity, suggesting that alterations in this system may be linked to ADHD (Leffa et al., 2019). Moreover, animal models of ADHD have demonstrated increase CB₁ receptor expression compared to Wistar rats (Haspula and Clark, 2016). In humans, ADHD has been associated with dysregulation of ECS metabolism (Centonze et al., 2009) and elevated plasma concentrations of AEA and 2-AG (Brunkhorst-Kanaan et al., 2021). Furthermore, genetic variations in ECS-related genes may also contribute to ADHD susceptibility (Ahmadalipour et al., 2020).

Given the high comorbidity between SUD and ADHD, we hypothesize that plasma concentrations of endocannabinoid-congeners may be altered in individuals with a history of alcohol and/or cocaine use, particularly in those with comorbid ADHD. To test this hypothesis, we conducted an exploratory study including healthy controls and abstinent SUD patients recruited from outpatient treatment programs. Additionally, a subgroup of SUD patients with comorbid ADHD was analyzed to explore potential alterations in plasma acylglycerol and acylethanolamide concentrations within this population. This study aims to identify potential biomarkers using machine learning to provide novel insights into the mechanisms underlying the comorbidity between SUD and ADHD. The analysis of these endocannabinoid-congeners may contribute to the identification of new diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, addressing the complex pathophysiological interactions associated with the comorbidity of both conditions, SUD and ADHD.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Participants and recruitment

This exploratory study included abstinent patients with alcohol and/or cocaine use disorder (AUD and/or CUD), along with healthy control subjects, comprising a total of 469 Caucasian participants divided into two primary groups: (1) the SUD group, consisting of 333 abstinent patients with a lifetime diagnosis of SUD, and (2) the control group, comprising 136 healthy subjects. The SUD group was further categorized based on the presence of comorbid ADHD, resulting in two subgroups: (1) the non-ADHD subgroup ($n = 267$), and (2) the ADHD subgroup (co-occurrence of SUD and ADHD, $n = 66$). Additionally, the potential influence of sex on plasma concentrations of endocannabinoid-congeners within the SUD group was examined. Participants in the SUD

group were recruited from outpatient treatment programs for alcohol and/or cocaine dependence at *Hospital Universitario 12 de Octubre* (Madrid, Spain), *Hospital Regional Universitario de Málaga* (Málaga, Spain), and *Centro Provincial de Drogodependencias de Málaga* (Málaga, Spain). These patients were part of a multicenter cohort from the Spanish Network for Addictive Disorders (*Red de Trastornos Adictivos - RETICS*). The 136 healthy control subjects, matched to the SUD group for age and body mass index (BMI), were recruited from a cohort of multidisciplinary staff volunteers working within the Spanish National Public Health System.

2.2. Eligibility criteria

Participation in the study was voluntary, and all participants were required to meet specific inclusion criteria. Eligible individuals were between 18 and 60 years of age, and those in the SUD group had to have a lifetime diagnosis of SUD. Exclusion criteria applied to all participants included a history of chronic inflammatory disorders, infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and COVID-19), cognitive or language impairments that could interfere assessment, pregnancy or breastfeeding, and current substance use, except for nicotine and caffeine. For the control group, additional exclusion criteria included a history of psychiatric disorders or problematic substance use. Ultimately, 21 patients and 10 control subjects were excluded based on these eligibility criteria.

2.3. Ethics statements

Each participant provided written informed consent after receiving a comprehensive briefing about the study. They were also given the opportunity to ask questions or express concerns before participation. The study and recruitment protocols were approved by the Regional Ethics Committee, specifically the *Sistema de Información de los Comités de Ética de la Investigación de Andalucía* (SICEIA) and the *Hospital Regional Universitario de Málaga*. The study adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki (Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects, 64th WMA General Assembly, Fortaleza, Brazil, 2013), as well as the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) for data protection and privacy within the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA). To ensure participant confidentiality and data privacy, all personal information was anonymized and assigned a unique code number.

2.4. Clinical evaluations

All participants underwent psychiatric evaluation through two structured interviews, tailored to their respective groups and subgroups, and conducted by trained and experienced psychologists. For patients, the Spanish version of the Psychiatric Research Interview for Substance and Mental Diseases (PRISM) was predominantly used. PRISM is a semi-structured interview developed according to DSM-IV-TR criteria, with strong validity and test-retest reliability for diagnosing substance-induced disorders and major mental disorders in populations with substance use (Hasin et al., 1996; Torrens et al., 2004). The variables collected included abstinence status, SUD severity (calculated by aggregating DSM-5 criteria for SUD), mental and medical comorbidities, and psychotropic medication usage. For control participants, the Spanish version of the Composite International Diagnostic Interview (CIDI) was used to assess mental disorders (Robins et al., 1988). Additionally, PRISM module 1 was administered to collect sociodemographic and physiological variables (Flores-López et al., 2021; Galván et al., 2021).

2.5. Collection and processing of plasma samples

Prior to the psychiatric interviews, blood samples were collected in the morning after overnight fasting. All participants were scheduled for

blood extraction between 8:00 and 9:00 am. Venous blood was drawn into 10 mL K₂ EDTA tubes (BD, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) and immediately processed to obtain plasma within 8–12 h. The blood samples were centrifuged at 2200 ×g for 15 min at 4 °C, and each sample was individually tested for infectious diseases using four commercial rapid tests for HIV, hepatitis B, and hepatitis C (Strasbourg, Cedex, France) and SARS-CoV-2 (Bio-Connect, Huissen, the Netherlands). Finally, plasma samples were individually characterized, recorded, and stored at –80 °C until further analyses.

2.6. Quantification of endocannabinoid-congeners in plasma samples

Endocannabinoid-congeners were measured in plasma using high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) following a previously described method (Pastor et al., 2014). The identified acylglycerols included 2-AG, 2-LG, and 2-OG. Additionally, the quantified acylethanolamides comprised AEA, DEA, DHEA, DGLEA, LEA, OEA, PEA, POEA, and SEA.

Briefly, 0.5 mL plasma aliquots were transferred to 12 mL glass tubes, spiked with deuterated internal standards, diluted with 0.1 M ammonium acetate buffer (pH 4.0), and extracted using tert-butyl methyl ether. The dried organic extracts were reconstituted in 100 µL of a water mixture (10:90, v/v) containing 0.1 % formic acid (v/v) and transferred to HPLC vials. A 20-µL sample was then injected into the HPLC-MS/MS system. The analysis was performed on an Agilent 6410 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Wilmington, DE, USA) equipped with a 1200 series binary pump, column oven, and cooled auto-sampler (4 °C). Chromatographic separation was achieved on an ACQUITY UPLC C18-CSH column (3.1 × 100 mm, 1.8 µm particle size) (Waters, Yvelines Cedex, France) maintained at 40 °C, with a mobile phase flow rate of 0.4 mL/min. The mobile phase consisted of (A) 0.1 % formic acid in water and (B) 0.1 % formic acid in acetonitrile. Quantification was performed using isotope dilution. Deuterated internal standards were sourced from Cayman Chemical (Ann Arbor, MI, USA), and solvents were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

2.7. Statistical analysis

Data are presented in tables as number and percentage [n (%)], mean and standard deviation (mean ± SD), or median and interquartile range [median (IQR)]. Categorical variables were compared using either the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, while continuous variables were assessed using the Student's *t*-test for normally distributed data or the Mann-Whitney *U* test for non-normally distributed data. The Benjamini-Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction was applied to control for multiple comparisons.

Two-way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to assess the main effects and interactions of the primary independent variables [i.e., SUD diagnosis (control and SUD groups) or ADHD diagnosis (non-ADHD and ADHD subgroups) and sex (women and men)] on plasma concentrations of endocannabinoid-congeners adjusting for age and BMI. Due to positive skewness in the data distribution, raw acylglycerol and acylethanolamide concentrations were log₁₀-transformed to meet the statistical assumptions of ANCOVA. Post hoc pairwise comparisons for significant interactions were conducted using the Sidak method. Figures display back-transformed estimated marginal means and 95 % confidence intervals (95 % CI) for log₁₀-transformed acylglycerol and acylethanolamide concentrations, enhancing interpretability.

Spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ) was used to evaluate associations between raw concentrations of endocannabinoid-congeners and age and BMI.

These statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism version 5.04 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA) and IBM SPSS Statistics version 22 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). A *p*-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

2.8. Machine learning analysis for biomarker evaluation

To assess the discriminative potential of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides as biomarkers for ADHD comorbidity in SUD, we implemented a multinomial Elastic Net regression model based on previous studies (Bunea et al., 2011; Tay et al., 2023). The Elastic Net regression is a regularized regression method that combines LASSO ($L1$) and Ridge ($L2$) regression. The dataset included 12 endocannabinoid-congeners as predictor variables and the three study groups as the categorical outcome variable: the control group (X_0), the non-ADHD subgroup (X_1), and the ADHD subgroup (X_2).

The model development process consisted of the following steps: (1) Biomarker selection and data preprocessing: Missing values were removed to ensure data integrity, endocannabinoid-congener concentrations were normalized using Z-score transformation, and effects of confounding variables such as BMI were adjusted via linear regression; (2) Handling class imbalance: Given the lower prevalence of the ADHD subgroup, oversampling was applied to X_2 , while X_0 and X_1 were undersampled to achieve class balance; (3) Dataset splitting: The dataset was randomly split once into 80 % training and 20 % testing sets using a fixed random seed to ensure reproducible results; (4) Model training: A multinomial Elastic Net regression was applied, combining $L1$ and $L2$ regularization to optimize feature selection and model stability (Hyperparameter tuning was performed using stratified 10-fold cross-validation, with alpha and lambda values optimized for the best model performance); and (5) Evaluation metrics: Model performance was assessed using accuracy, recall (sensitivity), specificity, balanced accuracy, and receiver operating characteristic area under the curve (ROC-AUC).

3. Results

3.1. Sociodemographic characteristics

Table 1 presents an overview of the sociodemographic characteristics of the study sample, divided into the SUD group and the control group. As expected, no significant differences were observed between

Table 1
Baseline sociodemographic characteristics.

Variables		Groups		P-value
		Control n = 136	SUD n = 333	
Sex n (%)	Women	47 (34.6)	67 (20.1)	0.001 ^a
	Men	89 (65.4)	266 (79.9)	
Age median (IQR)	Years	42.0 (37.0–49.0)	43.0 (34.0–51.0)	0.732 ^b
	BMI median (IQR)	kg/m ² 25.2 (22.7–27.7)	25.6 (23.0–29.1)	0.061 ^b
Education level n (%)	Primary	7 (5.1)	116 (34.8)	<0.001 ^a
	Secondary	48 (35.3)	170 (51.1)	
	University	81 (59.6)	47 (14.1)	
Work status n (%)	Employed	119 (87.5)	101 (30.3)	<0.001 ^a
	Sick leave	2 (1.5)	37 (11.1)	
	Unemployed	11 (8.1)	151 (45.3)	
	Retired/ Housework	4 (2.9)	44 (13.2)	
Marital status n (%)	Single	67 (49.3)	116 (34.8)	0.002 ^a
	Cohabiting/ Married	52 (38.2)	131 (39.3)	
	Divorced/ Separated	14 (10.3)	80 (24.0)	
	Widowed	3 (2.2)	6 (1.8)	

Abbreviations: BMI = body mass index; IQR = interquartile range; SUD = substance use disorder.

^a P-values using the Chi-square test.

^b P-values using the Mann-Whitney U test.

the groups in terms of age and BMI, with a median age of 41 years and a mean BMI of 25 kg/m². However, the proportion of men was significantly higher in the SUD group compared to the control group (80 % and 65 %, respectively; $p = 0.001$), consistent with the greater treatment demand among men than women.

Significant differences were identified between the groups in terms of educational attainment ($p < 0.001$), employment status ($p < 0.001$), and marital status ($p < 0.01$). A higher proportion of individuals in the control group had university education (60 %), whereas a greater percentage of participants in the SUD group had attained only primary or secondary education (86 %). Employment rates were markedly lower in the SUD group compared to the control group (30 % and 88 %, respectively). Additionally, marital status differed between the groups, with a higher prevalence of divorced individuals in the SUD group compared to the control group (24 % and 10 %, respectively).

3.2. Plasma endocannabinoid-congeners based on SUD diagnosis

The raw concentrations of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides were compared between the SUD and control groups using the Mann-Whitney

Table 2
Plasma concentrations of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides.

Variables	Groups		P-value ^a	
	Control n = 136	SUD n = 333		
2-AG median (IQR)	nmol/ L	4.58 (2.35–7.30)	3.16 (2.00–5.14)	<0.001
2-LG median (IQR)	nmol/ L	62.68 (37.33–128.57)	39.00 (20.25–73.10)	<0.001
2-OG median (IQR)	nmol/ L	36.55 (22.65–77.50)	31.00 (20.90–49.30)	0.061
AEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	0.36 (0.21–0.51)	0.44 (0.30–0.64)	<0.001
DEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	0.08 (0.05–0.15)	0.13 (0.09–0.18)	<0.001
DGLEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	0.07 (0.04–0.09)	0.08 (0.06–0.12)	<0.001
DHEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	0.44 (0.29–0.63)	0.52 (0.37–0.72)	0.003
LEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	0.72 (0.54–0.96)	1.08 (0.86–1.38)	<0.001
OEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	2.14 (1.36–3.23)	3.37 (2.52–4.51)	<0.001
PEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	1.66 (1.28–2.94)	3.37 (2.25–5.71)	<0.001
POEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	0.26 (0.15–0.38)	0.31 (0.19–0.43)	0.102
SEA median (IQR)	nmol/ L	4.78 (0.98–6.19)	2.05 (1.30–4.20)	0.025

Abbreviations: 2-AG = 2-arachidonoylglycerol; 2-LG = 2-linoleoylglycerol; 2-OG = 2-oleoylglycerol; AEA = arachidonoylethanolamide; DEA = docosate-traenoylethanolamide; DGLEA = dihomogamma-linolenoylethanolamide; DHEA = docosahexaenoylethanolamide; IQR = interquartile range; LEA = linoleoylethanolamide; OEA = oleoylethanolamide; PEA = palmitoylethanolamide; POEA = palmitoleoylethanolamide; SEA = stearoylethanolamide; SUD = substance use disorder.

^a P-values using the Mann-Whitney U test. P-values in bold indicate significant differences after applying the Benjamini-Hochberg correction for multiple comparisons

U test, as presented in Table 2. Significant differences were observed for all measured fatty acid-derived mediators, except for 2-OG and POEA. Specifically, the concentrations of 2-AG ($p < 0.001$), 2-LG ($p < 0.001$), and SEA ($p < 0.05$) were significantly lower in the SUD group compared to the control group. Conversely, the concentrations of AEA ($p < 0.001$), DEA ($p < 0.001$), DGLA ($p < 0.001$), DHEA ($p < 0.01$), LEA ($p < 0.001$), OEA ($p < 0.001$), and PEA ($p < 0.001$) were significantly higher in the SUD group than in the control group. Applying the Benjamini-Hochberg correction for multiple comparisons did not alter these significant findings.

3.3. Correlations between plasma endocannabinoid-congener concentrations and age and BMI

Despite the absence of significant differences in age and BMI between the groups, we assessed the associations between the raw concentrations of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides and these physiological variables within the sample. As shown in Table 3, Spearman's correlation coefficients revealed significant associations between specific endocannabinoid-congeners and both age and BMI in the overall sample and across groups after multiple correction. Notably, all significant correlations observed in the total sample were also present in the SUD group, whereas no significant associations were detected between endocannabinoid-congeners, age, and BMI in the control group.

3.3.1. Plasma endocannabinoid-congeners and age

In the SUD group, age was positively correlated with the concentrations of 2-OG ($\rho = +0.22, p < 0.001$) and POEA ($\rho = +0.20, p < 0.01$). In contrast, age was negatively correlated with the concentrations of AEA ($\rho = -0.33, p < 0.001$), DEA ($\rho = -0.29, p < 0.001$), DGLA ($\rho = -0.29, p < 0.001$), LEA ($\rho = -0.13, p < 0.05$), and SEA ($\rho = -0.24, p < 0.001$). In the control group, no significant correlations were observed between age and these mediators after multiple comparison correction.

Table 3

Correlation analyses between plasma concentrations of endocannabinoid-congeners and age and BMI.

Variables		Age (Years)			BMI (kg/m ²)		
		TOTAL	Control	SUD	TOTAL	Control	SUD
2-AG (nmol/L)	ρ	-0.056	+0.014	-0.076	+0.170	+0.195	+0.184
	P-value	0.223	0.873	0.166	<0.001	0.023	0.001
2-LG (nmol/L)	ρ	-0.044	-0.052	-0.031	+0.059	+0.037	+0.099
	P-value	0.338	0.545	0.572	0.201	0.665	0.071
2-OG (nmol/L)	ρ	+0.192	+0.116	+0.221	+0.208	+0.220	+0.218
	P-value	<0.001	0.311	<0.001	<0.001	0.053	0.001
AEA (nmol/L)	ρ	-0.218	+0.051	-0.331	+0.173	+0.215	+0.136
	P-value	<0.001	0.559	<0.001	<0.001	0.012	0.013
DEA (nmol/L)	ρ	-0.194	-0.014	-0.294	+0.175	+0.267	+0.135
	P-value	<0.001	0.903	<0.001	<0.001	0.018	0.033
DGLA (nmol/L)	ρ	-0.203	-0.003	-0.288	+0.173	+0.180	+0.151
	P-value	<0.001	0.972	<0.001	<0.001	0.036	0.006
DHEA (nmol/L)	ρ	-0.030	+0.108	-0.084	+0.139	+0.126	+0.132
	P-value	0.517	0.229	0.127	0.003	0.161	0.016
LEA (nmol/L)	ρ	-0.067	+0.051	-0.125	+0.169	+0.120	+0.160
	P-value	0.151	0.575	0.022	<0.001	0.184	0.003
OEA (nmol/L)	ρ	+0.049	+0.186	-0.004	+0.148	+0.197	+0.094
	P-value	0.312	0.038	0.942	0.002	0.027	0.102
PEA (nmol/L)	ρ	+0.021	+0.116	+0.034	+0.183	+0.193	+0.159
	P-value	0.690	0.200	0.609	0.001	0.032	0.015
POEA (nmol/L)	ρ	+0.184	+0.105	+0.204	+0.110	+0.072	+0.117
	P-value	0.003	0.518	0.003	0.083	0.658	0.091
SEA (nmol/L)	ρ	-0.136	+0.023	-0.240	-0.011	+0.083	-0.025
	P-value	0.010	0.802	<0.001	0.831	0.354	0.701

P-values in bold indicate significant differences after applying the Benjamini-Hochberg correction for multiple comparisons. Abbreviations: 2-AG = 2-arachidonoylglycerol; 2-LG = 2-linoleoylglycerol; 2-OG = 2-oleoylglycerol; AEA = arachidonylethanolamide; DEA = docosahexaenylethanolamide; DGLA = dihomogamma-linolenylethanolamide; DHEA = docosahexaenylethanolamide; IQR = interquartile range; LEA = linoleylethanolamide; OEA = oleylethanolamide; PEA = palmitoylethanolamide; POEA = palmitoylethanolamide; SEA = stearoylethanolamide; SUD = substance use disorder.

3.3.2. Plasma endocannabinoid-congeners and BMI

Regarding BMI, in the SUD group, significant positive correlations were found between BMI and the concentrations of 2-AG ($\rho = +0.18, p = 0.001$), 2-OG ($\rho = +0.22, p = 0.001$), AEA ($\rho = +0.14, p < 0.05$), DEA ($\rho = +0.14, p < 0.05$), DGLA ($\rho = +0.15, p < 0.01$), DHEA ($\rho = +0.13, p < 0.05$), LEA ($\rho = +0.16, p < 0.01$), and PEA ($\rho = +0.16, p < 0.05$). Conversely, no significant correlations were observed in the control group.

3.4. Plasma endocannabinoid-congeners based on SUD diagnosis and sex after adjusting for age and BMI

Plasma concentrations of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides were analyzed in relation to lifetime SUD in women and men. To meet the statistical assumptions of two-way ANCOVA, raw concentrations were log₁₀-transformed, with SUD diagnosis and sex as factors, adjusting for age and BMI. Figures show the back-transformed estimated marginal means and 95 % CI for acylglycerols and acylethanolamides.

3.4.1. Acylglycerols

The analysis revealed a significant main effect of SUD diagnosis on 2-AG ($F_{(1, 469)} = 15.51, p < 0.001$; Fig. 1A) and 2-LG ($F_{(1, 469)} = 26.69, p < 0.001$; Fig. 1B), with lower concentrations in patients with SUD compared to controls. In addition to the effects of SUD, there was a significant main effect of sex on 2-AG ($F_{(1, 469)} = 4.61, p = 0.032$; Fig. 1A) and 2-OG ($F_{(1, 329)} = 15.12, p < 0.001$; Fig. 1C), with women exhibiting lower concentrations than men. Furthermore, a significant interaction between the SUD diagnosis and sex was found for 2-OG ($F_{(1, 329)} = 6.27, p = 0.013$; Fig. 1C). Post hoc comparisons showed that in the control group, women had significantly lower 2-OG concentrations than men ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, both men and women with SUD had lower 2-OG concentrations compared to control men ($p < 0.01$).

3.4.2. Acylethanolamides

For acylethanolamides, a significant main effect of SUD diagnosis

Fig. 1. Plasma concentrations of acylglycerols based on SUD diagnosis and sex. (A) 2-AG concentrations; (B) 2-LG concentrations; and (C) 2-OG concentrations. Log₁₀-transformed acylglycerol concentrations were analyzed using two-way ANCOVA, adjusting for age and BMI. Bars represent the back-transformed estimated marginal means and 95 % CIs. F-statistics and p-values are indicated. (#) $p < 0.05$ denotes significant differences compared to men; (***) $p < 0.001$ denotes significant differences compared to the control group; (aa) $p < 0.01$ and (aaa) $p < 0.001$ denote significant differences compared to control men.

was observed for AEA ($F_{(1, 469)} = 18.94, p < 0.001$; Fig. 2A), DEA ($F_{(1, 469)} = 21.27, p < 0.001$; Fig. 2B), DGLEA ($F_{(1, 469)} = 27.18, p < 0.001$; Fig. 2C), DHEA ($F_{(1, 458)} = 4.84, p = 0.028$; Fig. 2D), LEA ($F_{(1, 458)} = 87.94, p < 0.001$; Fig. 2E), OEA ($F_{(1, 431)} = 58.44, p < 0.001$; Fig. 2F), PEA ($F_{(1, 431)} = 22.81, p < 0.001$; Fig. 2G), and SEA ($F_{(1, 357)} = 7.76, p = 0.006$; Fig. 2I). Specifically, patients with SUD had higher concentrations of all these endocannabinoid-congeners compared to controls, except for SEA, which was lower in the SUD group. A significant main effect of sex was also found for PEA ($F_{(1, 431)} = 4.28, p = 0.039$; Fig. 2G), with women exhibiting lower concentrations than men. No significant interactions between SUD diagnosis and sex were found for acylethanolamides.

3.5. Clinical characteristics related to SUD and psychiatric comorbidity

Variables associated with dual diagnosis, particularly lifetime SUD diagnosis, were evaluated (Table 4). The data indicate a high prevalence of AUD (40 % of the sample), with comorbid CUD in approximately 45 % of cases. The median age at onset of both AUD and CUD was similar,

ranging from 21 to 23 years. Patients with SUD met DSM-5 severity criteria, with mean scores of 7 for AUD and 6 for CUD, indicating severe SUD. The duration of substance uses varied, with a median of 10 years for AUD and approximately 4 years for CUD. In terms of abstinence, patients with AUD had a median abstinence period of 69 days, whereas those with CUD had a shorter median abstinence period of 25 days.

Regarding psychiatric comorbidity, 75 % of patients with SUD had at least one co-occurring psychiatric disorder. Mood disorders were the most prevalent (43 %), followed by anxiety disorders (28 %), personality disorders (26 %), ADHD (20 %), and psychotic disorders (11 %). Additionally, 61 % of patients with SUD had been prescribed psychiatric medications in the past year, most commonly anxiolytics (47 %) and antidepressants (40 %).

3.6. Comorbid ADHD diagnosis in the SUD group

ADHD is a developmental risk factor that precedes substance use and complicates the therapeutic management of SUD, which exhibited a high prevalence in the SUD group. Given that ADHD is often under-recognized as a target for intervention, this study investigates its potential association with alterations in plasma concentrations of endocannabinoid-congeners.

3.6.1. Clinical characteristics based on comorbid ADHD diagnosis

We stratified the SUD group into non-ADHD and ADHD subgroups to evaluate clinical characteristics related to lifetime SUD diagnosis (Table 5). Patients with SUD and comorbid ADHD exhibited a higher prevalence of co-occurring AUD and CUD (61 %) compared to the non-ADHD subgroup (41.0 %). Notably, SUD severity was greater in the ADHD subgroup, with a significantly higher median AUD severity score of 8 ($p < 0.001$). ADHD symptoms were assessed in the ADHD subgroup, showing a median hyperactivity-impulsivity score of 5 and a median inattention score of 6 (no differences were observed between these symptom domains). Regarding other comorbid psychiatric disorders, personality disorders were significantly more prevalent in patients with ADHD (44 %) compared to those in the non-ADHD subgroup (21 %) ($p < 0.001$); however, no differences were observed in psychiatric medication use between the two subgroup, except for antidepressants ($p < 0.05$), despite the absence of differences in mood disorders.

3.6.2. Plasma endocannabinoid-congeners based on comorbid ADHD diagnosis and sex after adjusting for age and BMI

We analyzed log₁₀-transformed concentrations of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides in patients with SUD using two-way ANCOVA, with comorbid ADHD diagnosis and sex as factors, adjusting for age and BMI. Back-transformed estimated marginal means and 95 % CI for these endocannabinoid-congeners were presented in the figures.

3.6.2.1. Acylglycerols. The analysis revealed a significant main effect of comorbid ADHD diagnosis on 2-AG ($F_{(1,332)} = 4.65, p = 0.032$; Fig. 3A) and 2-LG ($F_{(1, 332)} = 7.54, p = 0.006$; Fig. 3C), with patients in the ADHD subgroup exhibiting lower concentrations of both endocannabinoid-congeners compared to the non-ADHD subgroup. However, no significant main effect of sex or ADHD \times sex interaction was observed for acylglycerols.

3.6.2.2. Acylethanolamides. A significant main effect of ADHD diagnosis was observed for AEA ($F_{(1, 332)} = 5.68, p = 0.018$; Fig. 4A), DGLEA ($F_{(1, 332)} = 9.88, p = 0.002$; Fig. 4C), DHEA ($F_{(1, 332)} = 10.46, p = 0.001$; Fig. 4D), PEA ($F_{(1,231)} = 6.65, p = 0.011$; Fig. 4G), and SEA ($F_{(1, 231)} = 5.32, p = 0.022$; Fig. 4I). Patients with comorbid ADHD exhibited significantly lower concentrations of AEA, DGLEA, DHEA, and SEA compared to the non-ADHD subgroup. Conversely, SEA and the only mediator found at higher concentrations in the ADHD subgroup. Similar to acylglycerols, no significant main effect of sex or interaction was

Fig. 2. Plasma concentrations of acylethanolamides based on SUD diagnosis and sex factors. (A) AEA concentrations; (B) DEA concentrations; (C) DGLEA concentrations; (D) DHEA concentrations; (E) LEA concentrations; (F) OEA concentrations; (G) PEA concentrations; (H) POEA concentrations; and (I) SEA concentrations. Log₁₀-transformed acylethanolamide concentrations were analyzed using two-way ANCOVA, adjusting for age and BMI. Bars represent the back-transformed estimated marginal means and 95 % CIs. F-statistics and p-values are indicated. (#) $p < 0.05$ denotes significant differences compared to men; (*) $p < 0.05$, (**) $p < 0.01$, and (***) $p < 0.001$ denote significant differences compared to the control group.

observed for acylethanolamides.

3.7. Endocannabinoid-congeners as potential biomarkers for ADHD in the context of SUD

To further evaluate the biomarker potential of plasma endocannabinoid-congeners, a multinomial Elastic Net model was implemented. The final model was selected based on sample size, biomarker selection, and class balancing strategy. This model successfully classified the three study groups—control group (X_0), non-ADHD subgroup (X_1), and ADHD subgroup (X_2)—with an overall accuracy of 72.09 % (95 % CI: 56.33 %–84.67 %). Balanced accuracy exceeded 70 % across all groups, demonstrating that the model effectively mitigated the effects of class imbalance.

The model exhibited the highest sensitivity for control participants (X_0 : 92.3 %), with specificity of 83.3 %. For patients with SUD without ADHD (X_1), sensitivity was 65.2 %, whereas specificity reached 90.0 %. In contrast, classification performance for patients with SUD and comorbid ADHD (X_2) showed a lower sensitivity of 57.1 %, while specificity remained high at 86.1 %. The ROC-AUC was 0.77, indicating a good discriminative power (Fig. 5A).

Analysis of biomarker importance indicated that SEA (+0.993) was the strongest positive contributor to the classification of X_0 , while AEA

(−0.456) and PEA (−0.202) were negatively associated with this group. In contrast, AEA (+0.703) and OEA (+0.536) were more strongly associated with X_1 , whereas DEA (−0.732) and 2-OG (−0.340) exhibited negative associations. Among patients with comorbid ADHD (X_2), PEA (+1.009) had the strongest positive association, while SEA (−1.012) was negatively associated (Fig. 5B).

These findings suggest that patients with comorbid ADHD exhibit a distinct fatty acid-derived mediator profile, supporting the potential use of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides as biomarkers for dual diagnosis.

4. Discussion

Substance addiction is a complex and multifactorial disorder influenced by biological, psychological, and social determinants. Among the various factors contributing to the development and persistence of SUDs, comorbid psychiatric conditions, such as ADHD, ADHD have been identified as key modulators of addiction severity, clinical progression, and treatment outcomes. Identifying biomarkers associated with SUD and ADHD comorbidity could enhance early diagnosis, patient stratification, and personalized therapeutic interventions.

A growing body of preclinical and clinical evidence supports the involvement of the ECS in both substance addiction (Basavarajappa

Table 4

Clinical characteristics related to SUD and psychiatric comorbidity in the SUD group.

Variables		SUD group n = 333
Lifetime SUD n (%)	AUD	132 (39.6)
	CUD	52 (15.6)
	AUD and CUD	149 (44.7)
Age at onset of AUD median (IQR)	years	21.0 (16.0–31.0)
	years	23.0 (17.0–30.0)
Severity of AUD median (IQR)	Score (0–11)	7.0 (4.0–9.0)
	Score (0–11)	6.0 (4.0–9.0)
Duration of AUD median (IQR)	years	10.0 (4.0–17.0)
	years	4.0 (1.0–10.0)
Abstinence from alcohol median (IQR)	days	69.0 (2.0–210.0)
	days	25.0 (1.0–120.0)
Abstinence from cocaine median (IQR)	No	84 (25.2)
	Yes	249 (74.8)
Lifetime psychiatric comorbidity n (%)	Mood disorders ^a	143 (42.9)
	Anxiety disorders ^b	94 (28.2)
	ADHD	66 (19.8)
	Psychotic disorders ^c	36 (10.8)
	Personality disorders ^d	85 (25.5)
Psychoactive medication use (past year) n (%)	No	84 (25.2)
	Yes	204 (61.3)
	Antidepressants	132 (39.6)
	Anxiolytics	157 (46.8)
	Anticraving	76 (22.8)
	Antipsychotics	42 (12.6)

Abbreviations: ADHD = attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder subgroup; AUD = alcohol use disorder; CUD = cocaine use disorder; IQR interquartile range; SUD = substance use disorder.

^a Mood disorders included major depressive episode, dysthymia, mania episode, hypomania episode, and cyclothymia.

^b Anxiety disorders included specific phobia, social phobia, panic disorder, agoraphobia, generalized anxiety disorder, obsessive compulsive disorder, and posttraumatic stress disorder.

^c Psychotic disorders included schizophrenia, schizoaffective, schizophreniform, delusional disorder, psychotic disorder not specified, and brief disorder.

^d Personality disorders included borderline and antisocial disorders.

et al., 2003; Blanco et al., 2012, 2014; Fuentes et al., 2024; Karimi-Haghighi et al., 2023; Serrano and Parsons, 2011) and neurodevelopmental disorders, including ADHD (Haspula and Clark, 2016; Navarrete et al., 2020). However, the interplay between ECS dysregulation, substance use, and ADHD pathophysiology remains poorly understood. This study aimed to address this gap by analyzing plasma concentrations of acylglycerols (2-AG, 2-LG, and 2-OG) and acylethanolamides (AEA, DEA, DGLEA, DHEA, LEA, OEA, PEA, POEA, and SEA) in healthy controls and patients with SUD, with additional analyses of sex differences and ADHD comorbidity. Furthermore, multinomial Elastic Net regression was applied to determine the biomarker potential of these endocannabinoid-congener molecules.

4.1. Key findings and clinical relevance

Our findings can be summarized as follows: (1) Acylglycerol concentrations were generally lower in patients with SUD compared to healthy controls, except for 2-OG, which showed no significant difference; (2) Most acylethanolamides, with the exception of POEA and SEA, were elevated in patients with SUD relative to controls; (3) Significant correlations were observed between age, BMI, and plasma concentration of several endocannabinoid-congeners in the SUD group, whereas these

Table 5

Clinical characteristics related to SUD and psychiatric comorbidity based on ADHD diagnosis in the SUD group.

Variables		SUD subgroups		P-value
		Non-ADHD n = 267	ADHD n = 66	
Sex n (%)	Men	209 (78.3)	57 (86.4)	0.142 ^a
	Women	58 (21.7)	9 (13.6)	
Lifetime SUD n (%)	AUD	111 (41.6)	20 (30.3)	0.013 ^a
	CUD	47 (17.6)	6 (9.1)	
	AUD and CUD	109 (40.8)	40 (60.6)	
Age at onset of AUD median (IQR)	years	21.0 (17.0–31.75)	22.0 (16.0–30.0)	0.895 ^b
	years	24.0 (18.0–30.5)	20.5 (17.0–26.5)	0.068 ^b
Severity of AUD median (IQR)	Score (0–11)	6.0 (3.0–8.0)	8.0 (6.0–10.0)	<0.001 ^b
	Score (0–11)	5.0 (1.0–9.0)	7.0 (1.0–10.0)	0.113 ^b
Duration of AUD median (IQR)	years	10.0 (4.0–18.5)	11.0 (5.0–16.0)	0.473 ^b
	years	4.0 (1.0–9.0)	7.0 (3.0–14.0)	0.110 ^b
Abstinence from alcohol median (IQR)	days	80.0 (1.0–232.0)	60.5 (18.8–210.0)	0.418 ^b
	days	25.0 (1.0–120.0)	27.5 (1.0–90.0)	0.615 ^b
ADHD symptom score median (IQR)	Hyperactivity-impulsivity	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	5.0 (3.0–8.0)	<0.001 ^b
	Inattention	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	6.0 (4.0–9.0)	<0.001 ^b
Lifetime psychiatric comorbidity n (%)	Mood disorders	114 (42.7)	29 (43.9)	0.855 ^a
	Anxiety disorders	71 (26.6)	22 (33.3)	0.274 ^a
	Psychotic disorders	30 (11.2)	6 (9.1)	0.615 ^a
Psychoactive medication use (past year) n (%)	Personality disorders	55 (20.6)	29 (43.9)	<0.001 ^a
	Antidepressants	98 (36.7)	34 (51.5)	0.039 ^a
	Anxiolytics	122 (45.7)	35 (53.0)	0.326 ^a
	Anticraving	57 (21.3)	19 (28.8)	0.289 ^a
	Antipsychotics	30 (11.2)	12 (18.2)	0.189 ^a

Abbreviations: ADHD = attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder subgroup; AUD = alcohol use disorder; BMI = body mass index; CUD = cocaine use disorder; IQR = interquartile range; non-ADHD = non-attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder subgroup; SUD = substance use disorder.

^a P-values using the Chi-square test.

^b P-values using the Mann-Whitney U test.

associations were absent in controls; (4) Sex differences were evident, as women exhibited lower concentrations of 2-AG, 2-OG, and PEA compared to men. A significant interaction between SUD diagnosis and sex was detected for 2-OG, as levels were also reduced in men with SUD; (5) Comorbidity analysis revealed that 45 % of patients with SUD had co-occurring AUD and CUD, while 75 % had psychiatric comorbidities, including ADHD (20 %); (6) ADHD comorbidity was associated with lower concentrations of 2-AG, 2-LG, AEA, DGLEA, DHEA, and SEA, whereas PEA was significantly elevated in the ADHD subgroup; (7) Multinomial Elastic Net regression identified AEA, OEA, PEA, and SEA as the most relevant predictors for group classification, highlighting their potential role as biomarkers for dual diagnosis.

These findings provide further evidence of ECS dysregulation in SUD (García Marchena et al., 2016; García-Marchena et al., 2017; Navarrete et al., 2020; Pedraz et al., 2015) and suggest novel lipid alterations associated with ADHD comorbidity.

Fig. 3. Plasma concentrations of acylglycerols based on comorbid ADHD diagnosis and sex. (A) 2-AG concentrations; (B) 2-LG concentrations; and (C) 2-OG concentrations. Log_{10} -transformed acylglycerol concentrations were analyzed using two-way ANCOVA, adjusting for age and BMI. Bars represent the back-transformed estimated marginal means and 95 % CIs. F-statistics and p-values are indicated. (**) $p < 0.01$ and (***) $p < 0.001$ denote significant differences compared to the non-ADHD subgroup.

4.2. Role of ECS dysfunction in SUD and ADHD comorbidity

Our study confirms the high prevalence of co-occurring AUD and CUD in patients with SUD, along with significant rates of psychiatric disorders, consistent with prior literature (Fuster et al., 2024; Schuckit, 2006). The majority of studies on psychiatric comorbidity in the context of addiction have primarily focused on the most prevalent disorders, such as mood disorders, particularly major depression (Fuentes et al., 2024; García Marchena et al., 2016; García-Marchena et al., 2017; Pedraz et al., 2015). ADHD is another prevalent comorbidity in addiction (Aragonès et al., 2010; Vaziri-Harami et al., 2024), and our findings indicate that patients with comorbid ADHD exhibit more severe clinical profiles, characterized by increased polysubstance use, greater AUD severity, and a higher prevalence of personality disorders. These results demonstrate the importance of screening for ADHD and other psychiatric disorders in SUD populations, as comorbidities exacerbate substance use severity and complicate treatment (Lee et al., 2011; Maxwell, 2013; Pérez de Los et al., 2011).

Variations in the plasma concentrations of acylglycerols and

acylethanolamides were observed between patients of the SUD group with and without ADHD diagnosis. The lower concentrations of 2-AG and 2-LG in patients with comorbid ADHD suggest potential ECS dysfunction. Given the role of 2-AG in modulating reward pathways and emotional regulation, its reduction may indicate impaired endocannabinoid signaling, contributing to heightened vulnerability to addiction and more severe clinical presentations.

Previous studies have reported altered endocannabinoid metabolism in ADHD, including elevated plasma AEA and 2-AG concentrations (Brunkhorst-Kanaan et al., 2021; Centonze et al., 2009), though without considering SUD comorbidity. Our findings expand on this by demonstrating that patients with SUD (i.e., AUD and/or CUD) exhibited lower plasma 2-AG and 2-LG concentrations than healthy subjects, while most acylethanolamides – except POEA and SEA – were elevated. These results align with prior studies in AUD or CUD cohorts (García Marchena et al., 2016; García-Marchena et al., 2017; Pedraz et al., 2015). Endocannabinoids and related bioactive lipids are implicated in addiction-related processes (Bilbao et al., 2013; Serrano and Natividad, 2022; Serrano and Parsons, 2011). Distinct patterns of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides have been reported in various brain regions following drug exposure in rodent models (González et al., 2002; Serrano and Natividad, 2022), suggesting adaptive or compensatory mechanism ECS mechanisms. The differential expression of these bioactive lipids in patients with SUD underscores the potential of targeting endocannabinoid components for therapeutic interventions.

Finally, the reduction in AEA, DGLA, DHEA, and SEA in patients with comorbid ADHD suggests ECS-related lipid alterations specific to this comorbidity. Conversely, PEA concentrations were elevated in this subgroup, potentially due to dysregulated FAAH activity. Preclinical and clinical studies have reported that FAAH influence drugs exposure responses (Alegre-Zurano et al., 2023; Best et al., 2023), likely reflecting a compensatory mechanism to restore ECS homeostasis.

4.3. Sex differences and influence of age and BMI in endocannabinoid regulation

Biological sex also influences endocannabinoids and their congeners. Women exhibited lower 2-AG levels than men, with control women displaying lower 2-OG concentrations. Additionally, PEA levels were significantly reduced in women. Previous research from our group identified sex-based differences in POEA concentrations in patients with AUD and healthy controls (García-Marchena et al., 2017), a finding not replicated in this study, possibly due to higher comorbid substance use with CUD and a greater imbalance in sex distribution. Other studies have also reported sex-based lipid differences, particularly in arachidonic acid metabolism, from which 2-AG and AEA are derived (Amir Hamzah et al., 2023), highlighting the need for further research on sex-related ECS variations.

The relationship between endocannabinoid concentrations and physiological variables such as age and BMI is well-documented (Gao et al., 2022; Mattelaer et al., 2024). In the SUD group, 2-OG and most acylethanolamides correlated with age, whereas in controls, only OEA showed a significant correlation. Similarly, BMI-related correlations differed between groups, suggesting that aging and metabolic factors influence ECS activity differently in patients with SUD. These findings emphasize the need for personalized treatment approaches incorporating metabolic and demographic considerations.

4.4. Machine learning-based biomarker selection

To further assess the biomarker potential of endocannabinoid-congeners, a multinomial Elastic Net regression model was applied (Tay et al., 2023). This approach identified AEA, OEA, PEA, and SEA as key predictors of group classification, supporting their potential as biomarkers for ADHD comorbidity in SUD patients. Concerning acylglycerols, only 2-OG showed a smaller contribution. The model achieved

Fig. 4. Plasma concentrations of acylethanolamides based on comorbid ADHD diagnosis and sex factors. (A) AEA concentrations; (B) DEA concentrations; (C) DGLEA concentrations; (D) DHEA concentrations; (E) LEA concentrations; (F) OEA concentrations; (G) PEA concentrations; (H) POEA concentrations; and (I) SEA concentrations. Log₁₀-transformed acylethanolamide concentrations were analyzed using two-way ANCOVA, adjusting for age and BMI. Bars represent the back-transformed estimated marginal means and 95 % CIs. F-statistics and p-values are indicated. (*) $p < 0.05$, (**) $p < 0.01$, and (***) $p < 0.001$ denote significant differences compared to the non-ADHD subgroup.

an accuracy of 72.1 % (95 % CI: 56.3 %–84.7 %) and an ROC-AUC of 0.77, demonstrating moderate to good discriminative power. The biomarker relevance analysis indicated that SEA was the strongest predictor of the control group, whereas AEA and OEA were more characteristic of patients with SUD of the non-ADHD subgroup. Importantly, PEA was the primary predictor for comorbid ADHD in the SUD group, reinforcing its potential role as a marker of ADHD-related ECS dysregulation. These findings suggest that patients with SUD and comorbid ADHD diagnosis exhibit a distinct biochemical profile, which could facilitate better patient stratification and tailored interventions.

4.5. Limitations and implications for future research

Despite the promising findings of this study, several limitations must be acknowledged: (1) Sample size and composition: The relatively small sample, particularly in the ADHD subgroup, limits statistical power of the multinomial Elastic Net regression model in identifying biomarkers for SUD and ADHD. Additionally, it constrains the ability to conduct detailed stratified analyses (e.g., by sex or specific SUD types). Future studies should include larger and more diverse cohorts to validate these findings and examine potential sex differences more comprehensively. (2) Confounding factors: While we controlled for key demographic and physiological covariates (age, sex, and BMI), other potential

confounders such as socioeconomic status, education level, diet and nutritional status, physical activity, and medication use (D'Angelo and Steardo, 2024; Forteza et al., 2022; Tagliamonte et al., 2021; Tantimonaco et al., 2014) were not fully controlled for due to data availability limitations. Given that these factors may influence ECS-related biomarkers, future studies should incorporate more comprehensive assessments of these variables. Additionally, psychiatric medication use was recorded in the SUD group, and although no significant differences were found between ADHD and non-ADHD subgroups (except for antidepressants), future studies should investigate the potential impact of specific pharmacological treatments on endocannabinoid signaling; (3) Substance use severity and history: SUD-related variables may influence endocannabinoid-congener concentrations and could partially explain group differences. While we observed no significant differences in SUD onset, duration, or abstinence time between the ADHD and non-ADHD subgroups, our study design did not allow for a detailed assessment of cumulative substance exposure or progression of addiction over time. Future studies should consider integrating these variables using longitudinal models to better understand their impact on endocannabinoid dynamics. (4) Substance-specific effects and interaction with BMI: Given that AUD is associated with higher BMI and CUD with lower BMI, it would have been ideal to analyze these subpopulations separately in relation to BMI and ECS biomarkers. However, sample size limitations

Model performance metrics

METRIC	Control X_0	SUD		Overall Model Performance
		Non-ADHD X_1	ADHD X_2	
Sensitivity (Recall)	92.31	65.22	57.14	---
Specificity	83.33	90.00	86.11	---
Balanced Accuracy	87.82	77.61	71.63	72.09
ROC-AUC	---	---	---	0.766
Alpha (0-1)	---	---	---	0.6
Lambda	---	---	---	0.0149
Kappa	---	---	---	0.5605

Significant predictors in Elastic Net Model
Contributions by group

Fig. 5. Balanced Elastic Net regression model for SUD and comorbid ADHD. (A) Model performance metrics; (B) Biomarker contributions by (sub)group (X_0 , X_1 , and X_2) in the best-performing model.

prevented a robust stratification by specific SUD types, while also adjusting for age and BMI. Future research should explore substance-specific effects on endocannabinoid metabolism in larger cohorts, considering age, BMI, and potential interaction effects; (5) Temporal variability of endocannabinoid-congener levels: Endocannabinoid concentrations fluctuate over time, particularly during abstinence (García-Marchena et al., 2017). Our study focused on abstinent patients, and while abstinence duration did not differ significantly between SUD subgroups, we recognize the importance of longitudinal studies to assess ECS changes throughout different stages of addiction and recovery. Future research should employ repeated-measures designs to capture dynamic ECS alterations and their potential role in relapse risk. (6) Sleep and stress considerations: Sleep disturbances and stress are known to modulate ECS activity, but validated sleep assessments (e.g., polysomnography, actigraphy, self-reported sleep scales) and biomarkers of stress (e.g., cortisol levels) were not included in this study due to feasibility constraints (Kesner and Lovinger, 2020). Future studies should incorporate direct stress and sleep assessments to further elucidate their contributions to ECS dysregulation in SUD populations. (7) Therapeutic potential and clinical implications: While our findings suggest the relevance of targeting ECS components, additional studies should evaluate the efficacy of pharmacological interventions that modulate FAAH activity and PPAR- α pathways as potential treatment strategies for dual-diagnosis populations (Alegre-Zurano et al., 2023; Best et al., 2023); (8) Psychiatric comorbidity considerations: While prior research has focused primarily on mood and anxiety disorders in addiction (García Marchena et al., 2016; García-Marchena et al., 2017;

Pedraz et al., 2015), our study highlights the clinical complexity of ADHD as a comorbid condition in SUD. Given that patients with comorbid ADHD exhibited higher polysubstance use, greater AUD severity, and a higher prevalence of personality disorders, future research should further investigate the interactions between ADHD symptoms, psychiatric comorbidities, and ECS dysregulation in addiction.

In conclusion, while our study provides novel insights into ECS alterations in SUD and ADHD, future research should address these limitations through larger, longitudinal, and more controlled designs, incorporating comprehensive assessments of sleep, stress, inflammation, and psychiatric comorbidity to further elucidate the role of endocannabinoid signaling in addiction.

4.6. Conclusions

This exploratory study provides novel insights into ECS dysregulation in SUD and its comorbidity with ADHD, highlighting significant alterations in plasma concentrations of acylglycerols and acylethanolamides. Our findings suggest that ADHD comorbidity in SUD is associated with a more severe clinical profile, characterized by increased polysubstance use, greater AUD severity, and a higher prevalence of personality disorders. We identified distinct biochemical alterations in patients with SUD and comorbid ADHD, with reduced levels of 2-AG, 2-LG, AEA, DGLA, DHEA, and SEA, whereas PEA concentrations were elevated in this subgroup. These results point to potential ECS-related mechanisms underlying dual diagnosis and the need for targeted screening and intervention strategies. Furthermore, machine learning analysis using multinomial Elastic Net regression identified AEA, OEA, PEA, and SEA as key biomarkers, achieving an accuracy of 72.1 % and an ROC-AUC of 0.77. These results suggest that plasma acylglycerols and acylethanolamides may serve as potential biomarkers for ADHD comorbidity in SUD populations. Future research should focus on validating these findings in larger cohorts, investigating sex-specific variations of these endocannabinoid-congener mediators, and exploring pharmacological interventions targeting ECS components to enhance treatment outcomes in individuals with SUD and comorbid ADHD diagnosis. Expanding our knowledge of ECS dysregulation in dual-diagnosis populations could ultimately lead to more effective and personalized therapeutic strategies.

Ethics statements

Each participant provided written informed consent after being fully briefed about the study. They were also given the opportunity to ask any questions or express any concerns they had. The study and recruitment protocols received approval from the Regional Ethics Committee, specifically the Sistema de Información de los Comités de Ética de la Investigación de Andalucía (SICEIA) and the Hospital Regional Universitario de Málaga (Consejería de Salud y Familias, Junta de Andalucía). The study adhered to the ethical guidelines outlined in the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki (Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects, 64th WMA General Assembly, Fortaleza, Brazil, 2013), as well as the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) for data protection and privacy within the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA). To ensure participant confidentiality and data privacy, each participant's information was assigned a unique code number.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

María Flores-López: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jesús Herrera-Imbroda:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Nerea Requena-Ocaña:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Nuria García-Marchena:** Writing

– review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Pedro Araos:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Julia Verheul-Campos:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Juan Jesús Ruiz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Antoni Pastor:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Rafael de la Torre:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Antonio Bordallo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Francisco Javier Pavón-Morón:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Fernando Rodríguez de Fonseca:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Antonia Serrano:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Funding

This research was supported by the following grants: Projects funded by Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII) and cofunded by the European Union and ERDF-EU (PI19/00886, PI20/01399, PI22/00427 and PI22/01833); Programa RICORS RIAPAD funded by ISCIII and cofunded by the European Union (RD21/0009/0003 and RD24/0003/0012); Project funded by Delegación de Gobierno para el Plan Nacional sobre Drogas, Ministerio de Sanidad y Consumo (PNSD 2022/020); Programa Fortalece funded by ISCIII, Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades (FORT23/00013), and CTS-433 funded by Consejería de Economía, Innovación y Ciencia, Junta de Andalucía and ERDF-EU.

Declaration of competing interest

I have nothing to declare.

Acknowledgements

The authors express their gratitude to G. Rubio, M. Soria, and R. Campos for their invaluable support during the clinical phase of the study. Additionally, we would like to extend a special acknowledgement to all the patients and volunteers for their collaborative efforts.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpbp.2025.111350>.

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Glossary

- 2-AG: 2-arachidonoylglycerol
 2-LG: 2-linoleoylglycerol
 2-OG: 2-oleoylglycerol
 ADHD: attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder
 AEA: anandamide, arachidonylethanolamide
 ANCOVA: Analysis of covariance
 AUD: alcohol use disorder
 BMI: body mass index
 CIDI: Composite International Diagnostic Interview
 CUD: cocaine use disorder
 DEA: docosetraenoyl ethanolamide
 DGLEA: dihomogamma-linolenoyl ethanolamide
 DHEA: docosahexaenoyl ethanolamide
 ECS: endocannabinoid system
 FAAH: Fatty acid amide hydrolase
 LEA: linoleoyl ethanolamide
 OEA: oleoyl ethanolamide
 PEA: palmitoyl ethanolamide
 POEA: palmitoleoyl ethanolamide
 PRISM: Psychiatric Research Interview for Substance and Mental Diseases
 SEA: stearoyl ethanolamide
 SUD: substance use disorder